

LONG-TERM RESULTS AFTER RADIOFREQUENCY ABLATION OF PULMONARY VEINS AND FACTORS THAT INCREASE ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN PATIENTS WITH ATRIAL FIBRILLATION

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Resume. Like any invasive surgical intervention, RFA has its own range of possible complications, and therefore it is extremely important to predict the effectiveness of the operation in the preoperative period and determine the group of patients for whom this type of treatment is justified, and the predicted efficacy and safety are higher than possible complications. In the works of many authors (Bhargava M, et al. 2009; O'Neill M, et al. 2009; Hunter R, et al. 2010; Akoum N, 2011) identified a number of predictors of the likelihood of AF relapses in the postoperative period: persistent and long-term persistent form of AF, obstructive sleep apnea syndrome and obesity, increased LP size, old age, arterial hypertension and LP fibrosis according to cardiac MRI. Other researchers (Zado E, et al. 2008; Balk EM, et al., 2010) did not find an association of certain indicators with the probability of recurrence of arrhythmia after RFA

Keywords: antiarrhythmic drugs, antiarrhythmic, blood pressure, hypertension, diastolic blood pressure, coronary heart disease, computed tomography, pulmonary veins, left ventricle, left atrium.

Relevance. Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most common arrhythmia found in clinical practice. AF is associated with an increased risk of death, stroke and the frequency of hospitalization of patients (Kushakovskiy M.S., 2000; Ardashev A.V., 2001; Camm AJ, et al., 2012). Radiofrequency ablation (RF), a relatively recently proposed method of treating AF by Haissaguerre M. (1998) and Rarroppe S. (1999), is based on isolation of trigger sources of arrhythmia along the perimeter of the LV. The data accumulated to date indicate different effectiveness of the procedure: from 41-62% in persistent and permanent forms of arrhythmia to 64-86% in paroxysmal AF.

Like any invasive surgical intervention, RFA has its own range of possible complications, and therefore it is extremely important to predict the effectiveness of the operation in the preoperative period and determine the group of patients for whom this type of treatment is justified, and the predicted efficacy and safety are higher than possible complications. In the works of many authors, a number of predictors of the likelihood of AF recurrence in the postoperative period have been identified: persistent and long-lasting persistent form of AF, obstructive sleep apnea syndrome and obesity, increased LP size, old age, arterial hypertension and LP fibrosis.

The purpose of the work. To study the long-term results of RF LV in patients with AF, to determine the factors predicting the effectiveness of endovascular intervention.

Materials and methods of research. To solve these tasks, a sample of 249 patients with AF aged 21-74 years (mean age 54.9 ± 10.9 years) was consistently formed, of which 148 were men and 101 were women. The examination of patients was carried out at the clinical base of the BOKD, as well as at the cardiology clinic of 8 NMHC.

The results of the study. By the end of the first half of the follow-up, the connection with 4 patients was lost, their data were not used in further analysis. 169 out of 245 operated patients (69%) failed to register 14 AF attacks during scheduled visits, they had no subjective signs of arrhythmia, and a persistent sinus rhythm remained. In 76 (31%) patients, recurrent arrhythmias were verified, the frequency and duration of which differed significantly from patient to patient, although in most of them the average values of these indicators were significantly less than before surgery.

In a number of patients (21% of all people with recurrent AF), this required correction of drug-induced AAT, and in 26 (33% of all people with recurrent arrhythmia) - repeated RFA surgery. At the same time, 46% of individuals with verified AF relapse had rare short arrhythmia attacks with spontaneous recovery of sinus rhythm. In the second half of the postoperative period (6-12 months), communication with 37 patients was lost, and they were excluded from the subsequent analysis. Of the remaining 212 patients under observation, ~80% (n=167) had no recurrence of arrhythmia, and their operation was recognized as successful.

Among 45 patients who had a return of AF during this period, 9 (20%) patients required repeated RFA due to frequent relapses of paroxysms and their subjective significance. In the remaining 69% 31% without AF relapse, AF

relapses 79% 21% 15 cases either minor AAT correction was performed, or no additional interventions were performed. When analyzing the frequency and duration of AF attacks in people with recurrent arrhythmia, it was noted that both in the period of 3-6 months and in more distant periods (6-12 months), the frequency of AF attacks was more than 2 and 3 times less than before the RF - 4.6 ± 3.7 attacks / month. and 2.8 ± 3.4 seizures/month. vs 10.4 ± 8.2 seizures/month. Accordingly. During the analysis, no significant differences were found in any of the estimated 15 qualitative parameters, as well as indicators of systemic and intracardiac hemodynamics in individuals with recurrent arrhythmia compared with those in whom the RF operation was recognized as effective.

When studying the anatomical characteristics of LP and LV, it was found that individuals who developed a recurrence of arrhythmia 3-6 months after RFA initially had a significantly larger anteroposterior LP size - 4.5 ± 0.6 cm compared to those who had no AF attacks during this period - 4.2 ± 0.5 cm ($p < 0.05$).

In individuals with a return of arrhythmia in the period 3-6 months after RFA, the frequency of verification of abnormal confluence of LV in LP was significantly higher than in individuals with effective RFA - 39.3% vs 23.3%.

Among the patients who had a return of AF during this period, the overwhelming majority were men, and their percentage (80%) was significantly higher compared to the same indicator (63.1%) among people without a relapse of AF (Pearson coefficient $\chi^2 3.4$, $p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: 1. After 3-6 months after radiofrequency ablation performed for atrial fibrillation, a persistent sinus rhythm persists in 69% of patients, after 6-12 months – in 79%. Among people with recurrent arrhythmia at the specified time, the frequency and duration of atrial fibrillation attacks are significantly less than before the operation.

2. Factors that predict the recurrence of atrial fibrillation 3-6 months after radiofrequency ablation are the anteroposterior size of the left atrium, an abnormal variant of the pulmonary veins flowing into the left atrium, as well as the level of troponinemia in the first 6-12 hours after surgery. The equation of the discriminant function, which allows determining the probability of recurrence of arrhythmia with a sensitivity of 80% and a specificity of 77% during this period, in addition to the first two parameters, includes age and a long-lasting persistent form of arrhythmia.

3. The effectiveness of radiofrequency ablation in the second half of the year after surgery is influenced by factors such as gender, burdened heredity for atrial fibrillation, smoking, a long-lasting persistent form of arrhythmia and anteroposterior size of the left atrium. The discriminant function equation predicting with 67% sensitivity and 72% accuracy the risk of arrhythmia returning 6-12 months after surgery includes, in addition to the above factors, the presence of coronary heart disease in the anamnesis and the value of the heart rate before surgery.

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